

INFLUENCE OF MICROSTRUCTURE, STRESS GRADIENT AND DEFECT SIZE ON THE STABILITY OF THE CRITICAL DISTANCE METHOD FOR FRETTING CRACK NUCLEATION

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To prevent failure due to fretting and fretting-fatigue loading, it is important to understand the crack nucleation process and the influence of the microstructure and the geometries. This study aims to discuss the stability of the critical distance method with the grain size, the stress gradient and the crack nucleation length, in order to understand their impact on fretting crack nucleation. Cylinder/plane fretting tests were performed to determine experimental crack nucleation thresholds and use them in an elastic FEM simulation of the contact. Using an inverse method, a link has been established between the critical distance, the microstructure and the stress gradient. This study suggests that this link is very dependent on the considered crack nucleation length.

Keywords: Fretting, Crack nucleation, Microstructure, Finite-element method

INTRODUCTION

In many industrial applications, fretting can occur between parts in contact and be the origin of some severe damages such as cracking and wear. In partial slip regime, it leads to crack nucleation and brutal failure when combined with another loading such as fatigue. To prevent and understand that issue, lots of multiaxial fatigue criteria have been created (Smith *et al.* [1], Crossland [2], Papadopoulos *et al.* [3], etc.). In most multiaxial fatigue problems, these criteria are applied at the maximum of stress (the hotspot) where the crack will nucleate.

But, when there are high-stress gradients inside the bulk of the materials, these criteria overestimate the crack nucleation risk, which means they predict a smaller tangential load amplitude threshold for the initiation of the crack (Ferré *et al.* [4]).

In order to overcome that problem, one method that can be used is the critical distance method described by Taylor [5], which is a non-local approach. The idea of this method is to apply the fatigue criteria not at the hotspot but at a certain distance below the hotspot. This distance is called the critical distance ℓ (Figure 1) and needs an experimental/numerical coupling.

To overcome this experimental/numerical coupling problem which is expensive in time and material, Taylor [6] introduced an approximation for the critical distance: $\ell = b_0/2$ with b_0 the transition between short crack and long crack domains on the Kitagawa-Takahashi diagram (Kitagawa and Takahashi [7]). A lot of articles (Pinto *et al.* [8], Hattori *et al.* [9], Zabala *et al.* [10]) use this approximation and the formula of the El Haddad's parameter to calculate b_0 . As it only required the value of b_0 , this method is very simple to apply. However, there is no physical explanation behind the Taylor's approximation and does not consider any crack nucleation length.

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FIGURE 1 Definition of the critical distance (point method)

So, the objective of this study is to discuss the effect of microstructure and stress gradient over the critical distance and the fretting crack nucleation. As a consequence, one aim of this study is to determine a physical link between the critical distance, the grain size and the stress gradient. For this objective, we chose a medium-carbon steel (C35 steel) and performed heat treatments to modify its grain size. This change in microstructure leads to a change in the material properties that have been fully characterised by monotonic and cyclic tests. By obtaining all these properties, we suppose that we can decouple the effect of the microstructure over the critical distance and the fretting crack nucleation.

Finally, in order to discuss the influence of the crack nucleation critical length, three hypotheses have been considered: $b_{CN} = 0\mu\text{m}$ (theoretical threshold), $b_{CN} = d$ (mean diameter of a grain) and $b_{CN} = b_0$ (short cracks / long cracks transition on the Kitagawa-Takahashi diagram).

MATERIALS

The C35 steel (AISI 1038 / AFNOR XC38) is a medium-carbon steel with a 50-50 ratio of ferrite and perlite constituents. Thanks to several heat treatments, grain sizes from $3\mu\text{m}$ to $29\mu\text{m}$ have been obtained. The complete description of the heat treatment process and the grain size measurement is given in a previous article (Lannay *et al.* [11]). Five microstructures have been selected and are presented in Figure 2.

Tensile tests were performed to obtain the mechanical properties (Young's modulus E , Poisson's coefficient ν , yield stress σ_y and ultimate tensile strength σ_{UTS}) of the C35 steel for the five microstructures (cf. Table 1). As tensile tests were done only for three of the five microstructures ($d=6$, 12 and $29\mu\text{m}$), the values for $d=3\mu\text{m}$ and $d=20\mu\text{m}$ have been extrapolated. To validate these extrapolations, Vickers hardness tests have been performed for the five grain sizes. A Hall-Petch relation has been obtained for the hardness, the yield stress and the ultimate tensile strength (Figueiredo *et al.* [12]).

FIGURE 2 Microscope pictures of the different C35 steel microstructures after heat treatments

In order to apply the critical distance method, the tension-compression fatigue limit is needed. Fatigue tests using the “staircase” method were done for four of the five microstructures. Once again, the value for $d=3\mu\text{m}$ has been extrapolated. All the fatigue limits for 10^7 cycles are reported in Table 1.

Finally, to discuss the crack nucleation length influence and the $b_{CN} = b_0$ hypothesis, an inverse method as described by de Pannemaecker *et al.* [13] has been used to calculate the value of b_0 as a function of the grain size. The values of b_0 are compiled in Table 1. As we did not have enough fretting cracks for the $d=3\mu\text{m}$, we could not calculate its value of b_0 and had to extrapolate it.

TABLE 1 Mechanical properties for five C35 microstructures (*extrapolated values) [11]

d (μm)	3	6	12	20	29
E (GPa)	212*	210	207	202*	196
ν	0.28*	0.29	0.29	0.31*	0.32
σ_y (MPa)	629*	480	360	310*	280
σ_{UTS} (MPa)	797*	720	670	638*	620
HV	242	206	182	181	173
$\sigma_{d,-1}$ (MPa)	314*	280	239	237	229
b_0 (μm)	153*	179	170	187	236

So, all the mechanical properties have been obtained for the five selected materials.

FRETTING CRACKING ANALYSIS

Experimental process

In this study, cylinder/plane fretting tests have been done. The plane is made of the studied material (heat-treated C35 steel) and the cylinder is made of 100C6 steel (AISI 52100), both with an 8 mm width. The coefficient of friction between the two surfaces, equal to 0.9, has been obtained after a variable displacement fretting test.

These tests were done on a 100kN MTS hydraulic machine with most of the parameters fixed: normal load $P=4000\text{N}$, frequency $f=15\text{Hz}$ and number of cycles $N=1,000,000$. The only variable in this study is the amplitude of the tangential load Q^* which depends on the imposed displacement amplitude δ^* (as we are in the partial slip regime). Two experimental campaigns have been done: one with a fixed cylinder radius ($R_C=40\text{mm}$) and different grain sizes for the plane; one with a fixed microstructure ($d=12\mu\text{m}$) and different cylinder radii and so different stress gradients.

After each fretting test, the plane is cut along the median axis of the fretting scar, coated in epoxy and polished in order to reveal the cracks at the edge of the contact. Projected crack length b has been chosen as the measure of the crack length.

Fretting crack results

With these values, figures of projected crack length b as a function of the tangential load amplitude Q_{th}^* have been plotted for different grains sizes (Figure 3) and different cylinder radii (Figure 4). First, the fretting cracking behaviour is very dependent on the grain size (threshold at $0\mu\text{m}$ and slope of the fitting curve). The influence of the cylinder radius appears only on the value of the tangential load amplitude threshold at $0\mu\text{m}$.

As explained in a previous part, three crack nucleation lengths have been chosen: $b_{CN} = 0\mu\text{m}$, $b_{CN} = d$ and $b_{CN} = b_0$. So, for each grain size and each cylinder radius, three different tangential load amplitude thresholds have been defined as presented in Figure 5. All the values of tangential load amplitude thresholds are reported in Tables 2 and 3.

FIGURE 3 Projected crack length as a function of tangential load amplitude for different grain sizes of the C35 steel (Q^* tangential force amplitude; b projected crack length).

FIGURE 4 Projected crack length as a function of tangential load amplitude for different cylinder radii (C35 steel; Q^* tangential force amplitude; b projected crack length).

FIGURE 5 Crack nucleation length hypotheses

TABLE 2 Crack nucleation tangential load amplitudes (Q_{CN}^*) for different crack nucleation lengths (b_{CN}) and grain sizes (d) of the C35 steel ($R_C=40\text{mm}$).

d (μm)	3	6	12	20	29
$Q_{CN}^* (b_{CN}=0\mu\text{m})$ (N/mm)	170	179	154	161	112
$Q_{CN}^* (b_{CN}=d)$ (N/mm)	171	181	160	180	149
$Q_{CN}^* (b_{CN}=b_0)$ (N/mm)	246	242	243	334	395

TABLE 3 Crack nucleation tangential load amplitudes (Q_{CN}^*) for different crack nucleation lengths (b_{CN}) and cylinder radii (R_C) of the C35 steel ($d=12\mu\text{m}$).

R_C (mm)	20	40	80
$Q_{CN}^* (b_{CN}=0\mu\text{m})$ (N/mm)	139	154	170
$Q_{CN}^* (b_{CN}=d)$ (N/mm)	144	160	176
$Q_{CN}^* (b_{CN}=b_0)$ (N/mm)	213	243	258

So, thanks to this fretting crack analysis, crack nucleation thresholds were obtained that will allow us to perform FEM simulation and apply the critical distance method.

STABILITY OF THE CRITICAL DISTANCE METHOD

FEM modelling

A 2D FEM model of the cylinder/plane contact was created with an ABAQUS/Standard code (Figure 6). All the geometries and materials were the same as in the experimental device (cylinder made of 100C6 steel with a R_C radius, plane made of heat-treated C35 steel). The contact was defined as Lagrangian with a finite sliding formulation and friction coefficient equal to 0.9. Just under the contact (1.2 mm large, 0.5mm deep) the mesh was composed of quadrilateral elements with a mesh size of $5\mu\text{m}$. For boundary conditions, the plane was embedded ($U1=U2=UR3=0$) and the cylinder was blocked in rotation ($UR3=0$). Then, we applied the normal load ($P=500\text{N/mm}$) and the tangential load Q (related to the real experimental crack nucleation threshold) to the contact. In this paper, all the simulations were performed in elastic, neglecting the plastic behaviour of the C35 steel.

With the values of the stress distributions, the SWT equivalent stress [1] was calculated under the contact. We could observe a maximum at the edges of the contact (hotspots) just as predicted, where the cracks experimentally nucleate. Then the evolution of this SWT equivalent stress was extracted in the depth of the plane from one of the hotspots (Figure 7).

FIGURE 6 2D cylinder/plane FEM model with refined mesh under the contact

FIGURE 7 2D cylinder/plane FEM model with refined mesh under the contact

Fretting calibrated critical distance

Thanks to the experimental results and the numerical simulations, the critical distance was calculated for the five different microstructures, the three different cylinder radii (and so different stress gradients) and the three crack nucleation length hypotheses. The values of critical distance as a function of the grain size are reported in Table 4 and plotted in Figure 8. The values of critical distance as a function of the stress gradient are reported in Table 5 and plotted in Figure 9.

We can observe that, for the small crack nucleation lengths ($b_{CN} = 0\mu m$ and $b_{CN} = d$), the critical distance is constant with the grain size and with the stress gradient. This tends to confirm that the critical distance does not depend on the microstructure and the stress distribution just as many papers assured it (McCarthy *et al.* [14], Said *et al.* [15], etc.).

However, for $b_{CN} = b_0$, the critical distance linearly increases with the grain size and slowly decreases with the stress gradient. Considering this crack nucleation length hypothesis, it seems that the microstructure has a big influence over the critical distance. But, the evolution of the critical distance as a function of the stress gradient is contrary to what we expected and what we could see in the literature (Fouvry *et al.* [16]).

TABLE 4 Critical distance (ℓ) for different crack nucleation lengths (b_{CN}) and grain sizes (d) of the C35 steel ($R_c=40mm$).

d (μm)	3	6	12	20	29
$\ell_{(b_{CN}=0\mu m)}$ (μm)	27	35	32	36	21
$\ell_{(b_{CN}=d)}$ (μm)	27	36	35	44	34
$\ell_{(b_{CN}=b_0)}$ (μm)	56	62	73	134	191

FIGURE 8 Critical distance established for the SWT criterion (ℓ) as a function of the grain size (d) for different crack nucleation lengths (b_{CN}) (C35 steel, $R_C=40\text{mm}$)

TABLE 5 Critical distance (ℓ) for different crack nucleation lengths (b_{CN}) and cylinder radii (R_C) of the C35 steel ($d=12\mu\text{m}$).

R_C (mm)	20	40	80
$\ell_{(b_{CN}=0\mu\text{m})}$ (μm)	29	32	29
$\ell_{(b_{CN}=d)}$ (μm)	31	35	31
$\ell_{(b_{CN}=b_0)}$ (μm)	54	73	72

FIGURE 9 Critical distance established for the SWT criterion (ℓ) as a function of the stress gradient ($\nabla\sigma_{H,max}$) for different crack nucleation lengths (b_{CN}) (C35 steel, $d=12\mu$ m)

So, we obtain values of the critical distance for different conditions (microstructure, stress gradient, crack nucleation length) that will allow us to discuss the effect of these parameters over the fretting crack nucleation.

DISCUSSION

As said previously, for $b_{CN} = 0\mu$ m and $b_{CN} = d$, the critical distance is always constant. This conclusion leads to say that we only need to calculate the critical distance once (for one microstructure and one set of geometries) and then we can apply it to all the other conditions. So, the critical distance method seems to be stable with the microstructure and the stress gradient.

But, in the case of $b_{CN} = b_0$, an evolution of the critical distance with the grain size is noted. As a similar link was determined between b_0 and d , the ratio $\psi = \ell/b_0$ was calculated and plotted as a function of the grain size in Figure 10. Unlike what Taylor said, this ratio is not a constant equal to 0.5. It appears that this ratio linearly increases with the grain size. This leads to say that the Taylor’s approximation is not that bad in the first order but has limits when the variation in the grain size is too important.

FIGURE 10 Critical distance established for the SWT criterion (ℓ) as a function of the stress gradient ($\nabla\sigma_{H,max}$) for different crack nucleation lengths (b_{CN}) (C35 steel, $d=12\mu\text{m}$)

CONCLUSION

To conclude, we demonstrated that, considering small crack nucleation length ($b_{CN} = 0\mu\text{m}$ and $b_{CN} = d$), the critical distance is always constant regardless of the microstructure and the stress gradients, which tends to say that the critical distance method is very stable.

But, we also showed that, for long crack nucleation length ($b_{CN} = b_0$), there is a link between the critical distance and the microstructure which is more complex than the relation introduced by Taylor ($\ell = b_0/2$).

All this study highlighted the importance of taking into account the influence of the microstructure and the stress gradients to discuss the crack nucleation properties in the case of fretting. However, all the numerical simulations here were performed considering only the elastic behaviour of the C35 steel but it would be interesting to investigate the effect of plasticity over the fretting crack nucleation process and the critical distance method.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

b	projected crack length (μm)
b_0	short/long cracks transition (μm)
b_{CN}	crack nucleation length (μm)
d	grain size (μm)
HV	hardness Vickers
ℓ	critical distance (μm)
P	normal load (N/mm)
Q^*	tangential load amplitude (N/mm)
Q_{th}^*	crack nucleation tangential load amplitude (N/mm)

R_C	cylinder radius (mm)
z	depth under the fretting contact (mm)
Γ_{SWT}	SWT criterion parameter (MPa)
δ^*	fretting displacement amplitude (μm)
$\sigma_{a,-1}$	tension-compression fatigue limit with a -1 ratio (MPa)
σ_{SWT}	SWT equivalent stress (MPa)
ψ_ℓ	ℓ/b_0 ratio

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